

ORGANIZATION AND CONTENT OF EDUCATIONAL WORK IN KINDERGARTEN

Kashkinbayeva Zagira Kojabergenovna

Candidate of pedagogical sciences, Associate Professor Taraz Regional University named after
M.Kh.Dulaty (Taraz, Kazakhstan)

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Abstract. *The article considered the pedagogical foundations of the organization of educational work in kindergarten, studied the theoretical side of the issue, focused on the works of domestic and foreign scientists.*

Keywords: *kindergarten, preschool child, educational work, forms of educational work.*

Аннотация. *В статье рассмотрены педагогические основы организации воспитательной работы в детском саду, изучена теоретическая сторона вопроса, акцентировано внимание на работах отечественных и зарубежных ученых.*

Ключевые слова: *детский сад, дошкольник, воспитательная работа, формы воспитательной работы.*

In the XXI century, changes in the field of Education have led to the emergence of many modern problems. One of them is the peculiarities of organizing educational work in a preschool organization, that is, the development of educational technologies. The formation of preschool education is one of the most pressing issues of modernizing the system of preschool education.

Organization of educational work in a preschool organization – finding ways to effectively perform active forms of work with a child. Educational work is a process aimed at developing and improving the child's body, mind, and moral qualities [1;15]. Therefore, the organization of educational work in a preschool organization is a system consisting of a complex of work on the comprehensive development of a child. In addition, the organization of educational work in a preschool organization in a game version provides an easy implementation of educational work.

Develops an annual plan for the activities of a preschool organization in accordance with the requirements of the state mandatory educational standard of preschool education and training. In the work of a preschool organization, educational work is considered one of the main sections. The program of all works carried out in the preschool organization was approved and tested in stages. In general, kindergarten is the starting point of all education. In addition, the kindergarten is an organization that works closely with the family and parents.

The foundation for the formation of individual abilities and spiritual values of preschool children is laid by kindergarten. Improves children's social abilities, such as the ability to get along, perform roles, help, receive tasks, and perform tasks. In kindergarten, the activity of a teacher is carried out in teaching a child to perform tasks, creating a subject-developing environment for development. The creative activity of all teachers, i.e. specialists of preschool organizations, is expressed in a joint collective form. Tasks for managing the education system in a preschool organization are related to: collecting, analyzing, monitoring statistical reports on the problem of education, setting long-term goals.

In the planning of educational work, the world experience, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the child, is guided by modern goals and objectives of preschool pedagogy [2]. Methodological activity in the work of a preschool organization, the choice of

effective methods and methods of management-contributes to the correct formation of pedagogical management.

Management of the educational process is guided by the following principles::

- respect and trust in the child's personality;
- cooperation with the child;
- innovation;
- establishing partnerships with parents.

The main responsible persons in the organization of educational work are methodologists and teachers of preschool organizations.

The preschool organization carries out all the necessary work for the upbringing of children, in particular, health-improving, healing, hardening, and physical development related to the child's health. The results and indicators of the educational work carried out here are analyzed during the year and at the end of the year. Therefore, the upbringing of children will be one of the most pressing issues facing society. Educational work depends on the expansion of the spiritual world of the child's development.

Educational work performs the following tasks::

- organizational: regulates the Coordination of interaction of children participating in the educational event;
- regulatory: allows you to regulate social relations;
- informational: promotes the accumulation of new data.

In a broader sense, education is the transfer of adult social experience to a child, which ensures the preparation of the child for life and work. In a narrow sense, it is a purposeful and purposeful process aimed at the formation of the child's personal qualities. In a local sense, we can call the formation of one of the individual qualities of the child, discipline, and ethics.

In order to properly organize the educational process and prepare children for school in a preschool Organization, clear principles and methods are needed. In the organization of educational work with children in the activities of preschool organizations, educational work is planned and carried out in the areas of development of intelligence, intelligence, aesthetic abilities and tastes, hard work and hard work, physical development and strength, etc. [3]. According to the type of external organization, the forms of education are divided into two parts: group and collective. The group Type includes: children's matinees, Creative Works, small circles. The collective type includes children's stage performances related to various significant holidays, parties, trips, and sports competitions.

Conducting educational work with children should be a daily plan for the teacher to improve their skills. In our people, it is necessary to adhere to the proverb" do not educate your child with your own upbringing, educate your nation with your own". Therefore, it is necessary to influence the child's consciousness in all educational activities to learn the language, religion, traditions and customs of their nation. A kindergarten specialist can find his way to the child's heart only when he is a seeker, a master. All educational measures should contribute to the child's personality. For this purpose, kindergarten specialists should improve their professional skills in special courses. Pedagogical work is a characteristic of creativity. Therefore, the teacher must be a creative person.

Children are the future of our country. The essence of kindness and upbringing, which is given to the child from an early age, is the food of his life. At the same time, the issue of providing a child with advanced educational directions, demonstrated by world experience, is relevant today.

Only then will the child become closer to the search, creative work, and the result of educational activities will be positive.

The organization of work on the upbringing of preschool children in a preschool organization is not on the agenda. The content of all types of education is to improve the child physically and spiritually. Improving the quality and effectiveness of pre – school education is one of the most pressing problems of modern pedagogical science. Proper development of the child's body, normal psychological and behavioral norms require the implementation of various educational activities. Educational work is carried out in several areas. One of them: physical education. Physical education of preschool children considers the issues of improving the functions of the child's body, increasing performance, and strengthening health. Despite the rapid maturation of the body, the deterioration of its activity and defense abilities quickly leads to the fact that the child is exposed to adverse external influences and becomes ill [4].

Therefore, it is necessary to promote the timely maturation of the child's bone and joint apparatus, the correct formation of the lumbar spine, and the correct maturation of the soles of the feet. It is necessary to promote the development of all organs of the child's body, muscles, cardiovascular system, skeletal bones, respiration, nervous system and sensory organs. The main goal of physical education is to improve children's movements, develop motor skills and flexibility of the body.

Conditions necessary for the formation of a child's physical education:

- personal temperament, good knowledge of character traits, tastes and attitudes;
- determine the level of formation of qualities of interest, motivation, value judgment, etc.;
- gradually complicate the work of involvement in educational activities;
- change the tactics of education in case of difficulties;
- more confidence in your own activity and strength;
- focus on achieving success, guided by activity, independence.

In the development of a primary school student, attention was drawn to the fact that the history of the development of Physical Culture began very early. At the same time, it was determined that at each stage of Social Development, the requirements, desires, and demands for types of Education change. The preschool period is the time of formation of a child's intelligence. At this stage, the child begins to be imitative, impressionable, learn to speak and think. In preschoolers, there is a regularity of intelligence, the beginning of normalization of language and speech [5]. At this time, the child begins to express his inner self.

Educational plan-systematization of pedagogical influence, ensuring the fulfillment of pedagogical requirements, consistency and effectiveness of management of educational measures established in it. The educational plan contains a strategic goal, forms of its implementation, topics and directions that correspond to the age characteristics of pupils.

Direction 1: improving the content and quality of educational activities;

Direction 2: inclusion of types of educational activities that correspond to the individual and individual characteristics of pupils;

Direction 3: formation of criteria for evaluating the upbringing of pupils.

If we look at how the goal of education changes, we can see how important it is to define the goal of Education. Education is a social phenomenon, without which the life of any society is impossible to advance. Therefore, the comprehensive development of the individual is a single whole of the development of the body and mind [6].

In preschool age, the child develops the structure of the body and mind together, and moral qualities are formed. The child is immersed in the work of thought, learns the richness of spiritual life, is prepared to work actively in the spheres of society, and is formed morally.

The implementation of the general goal of education is the interrelated implementation of Educational Directions. It depends, of course, on the skills and general training of the teacher. The educational process is aimed at forming the most important educational qualities of the child, expanding the circle of communication with society, people and yourself. Therefore, the educational process is built in accordance with the harmonious formation and development of students in a full-fledged social environment.

Requirements for educational plans:

- Purposefulness: compliance of education with the requirements of society, goals;
Ch reality: compliance of forms and methods of education with the age and individual characteristics of children;
- Diagnostic: constantly study the requirements of educational work, monitor progress or make forecasts;
- Continuity: compliance with the principles of continuity, consistency, and connection in educational work;
- Effectiveness: achieving the goal and obtaining its results.

The teacher needs to know when planning educational work:

- * Goals and objectives of Education;
- * Age of pupils, level of development of groups of children, conditions of Education;
- * It is necessary to clearly define the educational plan and the time of its implementation.
- * Principles of educational work:
- * Purposefulness of educational work;
- * Taking into account the age characteristics of pupils;
- * Consistency of educational work;
- * Take into account the creative nature of educational work.

When planning educational work, it is necessary to take into account the following conditions::

- knowledge of the results and conclusions of educational work;
- knowledge of organizational and pedagogical tasks of educational work;
- knowledge of the methodological system of educational work;
- knowledge of best practices.

One of the most important tasks is to study the theoretical and methodological foundations of educational work in the development of a child's personal qualities, develop the structure and content in accordance with the age characteristics of the child. The educational plan is a document that combines comprehensive methods of developing the spiritual and physical qualities of a child. It is necessary to clarify and take into account the terms and means of its implementation, laws and principles. The role of teachers in the direction of adapting the child to the environment and improving his personal qualities is the beginning. For this purpose, collective participation in socially significant sports, cultural, art, education, science, etc. activities for the development of the child is of great importance. The child should grow up aware of the care and conditions created by the state, understanding his duty to society.

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